

Studies on the adsorption of gelatin on a synthetic hydroxyapatite

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The adsorption of gelatin onto hydroxyapatite has been studied at room temperature. The adsorption follows the Langmuir type of adsorption process. From the adsorption isotherm, various parameters such as the adsorption coefficient and rate constants for adsorption and desorption are evaluated. The adsorption is sensitive to variation in concentration of gelatin solution, pH of the suspension and temperature.

Calcium phosphates are intimately associated with biological constituents in bones and teeth and suitable materials for applying medical implants¹. Because of the high affinity of calcium phosphates for biomolecules, the interactions of proteins with colloidal calcium phosphates in aqueous media have been the subject of numerous studies. In particular, the adsorption of proteins by calcium hydroxyapatites ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$; CaHAP) has been given much attention by various authors² because it is a major inorganic constituent in bone and teeth, called mineral apatite. Hydroxyapatite in water has different surface charge densities caused by dissociation of lattice ions and adsorption³. The proteins have also highly solvated coils with exterior portions having strongest interaction with the solid adsorbent. The complex internal and external surface architectures of proteins in aqueous solutions are of primary importance in their adsorption behaviour. In the present communication we report the results of the adsorption of gelatin onto CaHAP from aqueous solution.

Results and Discussion

Ir spectra : The HAP showed two ir bands at 3521 and 3600 cm^{-1} due to OH^- ions on lattice sites and P-OH groups respectively. Three absorption bands at 3659, 3673 and 3682 cm^{-1} were reported earlier⁴ for the P-OH groups but we have obtained only one peak at 3600 cm^{-1} . The reason for the discrepancy may be due to the fact that in the present case the HAP was prepared under atmospheric oxygen.

Concentration effect : The concentration effect was studied in the range 15.3×10^{-6} to 76.9×10^{-6} mol dm^{-3} . The results indicate that the adsorption increases with increasing concentration of the protein solution.

Adsorption isotherm : In present case the adsorption isotherm belongs to S-types, i.e. a special class of Langmuir isotherm, a less commonly reported isotherm⁵. The adsorption coefficient K ($=k_1/k_2$) was calculated by using the linearized Langmuir equation,

$$\frac{C_e}{a} = \frac{1}{a_s K} + \frac{C_e}{a_s} \quad (1)$$

where, C_e is the equilibrium concentration of the gelatin solution, a the adsorbed amount at equilibrium concentration and a_s the adsorption capacity at saturation. The numerical value of K has been calculated to be 0.08×10^6 $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{dm}^3$.

Adsorption kinetics : Normally, the adsorption of a large molecule consists mainly of the following three steps⁶ : (i) transport of molecules towards the surface from the bulk of the protein solution, (ii) detachment of molecules at the active sites of the surface, and (iii) change in the conformation of the adsorbing macromolecule.

Fig. 1. Variation in adsorbed amount of gelatin with time for fixed [gelatin] = 61.2×10^{-6} mol dm^{-3} , HAP = 0.2 g, pH = 5.7, temp. = $27 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

Under the existing experimental conditions of agitating gelatin-hydroxyapatite suspensions, step (iii) can be ignored to have much lesser effect on the adsorption rate. The result of the variation of gelatin adsorbed indicates that the adsorption increases gradually with time and attains a limiting value after a definite period. It also reveals from Fig. that a constant adsorption rate is noticed upto 40 min, which thereafter decreases exponentially. Such a kinetic behaviour of adsorption of proteins is well recognized^{7,8}.

Thus, assuming the initial adsorption rate to be diffusion-controlled the following eq. can be written,

$$q = 2 C_0 \left(\frac{D_s t}{\pi} \right)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where the notations involved have their usual meanings. Obviously, with the help of a plot between q and \sqrt{t} , the diffusion constants of gelatin was calculated to be $8.6 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the given initial concentration of gelatin ($61.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$).

When we consider the later portion of the curve (Fig. 1) it appears as there is an activation barrier of adsorbed gelatin chains which governs the kinetics because the protein molecules arriving from bulk solution have to diffuse across the barrier. Thus, following the eq. suggested by Ligoure and Leibler⁹ we can write,

$$q = q_e [1 - \exp(-t/T)]$$

where q_e is the equilibrium adsorbed amount and T the characteristic penetration time. This eq. is identical to the first order kinetics eq. as reported by Sarkar and Chatteraj¹⁰. When a plot is drawn between $-\ln(q_e - q)$ and t , the penetration rate constant ($1/T$) was found to be $2.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$.

Rate constants k_1 and k_2 : The following equation¹¹ was used to calculate k_1 ,

$$\frac{1}{C} = k_1 \frac{1}{C_0} t + \frac{1}{C_0}$$

The value of k_1 is calculated to be $4.89 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$. Again, from the values of k_1 and K , the value of k_2 is calculated to be $6.12 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$.

Temperature effect : Temperature effect was studied in the range of 5–45° (Fig. 2). The results indicate an increase in adsorption with increasing temperature due to the following reasons : (i) the number of charged active sites on the HAP surface increases due to increased dissociation of lattice ions¹² with the rise in temperature, and (ii) the relative viscosity of the gelatin solution decreases with the increase in temperature (1.67 at 5°, 1.21 at 30° and 1.10 at 45°), which results in a faster diffusion of gelatin molecules towards the HAP surface.

pH effect : The pH effect has great significance in especially those systems where a polyelectrolyte molecule such as protein adsorbs on a polar surface¹³. In the present case, the effect of pH was studied in the range 3.5–11.3 by adding 0.1 N HCl and 0.1 N NaOH. It was found that gelatin started precipitating at pH <3.5, turning dense white. Therefore, the adsorption experiments could not be performed at pH lower than 3.5. Most often, a maximum adsorption is observed at the isoelectric point of the protein, but in the present case maximum adsorption occurs at 3.5 which is well below the isoelectric point of the gelatin (4.8). This is due to the shift in the isoelectric point towards

the acidic range. Hence, pH 3.5 may be considered as the new isoelectric point at which the gelatin molecules possess no net charge and thus maximum adsorption is exhibited. The shift in isoelectric point has also been reported by many workers¹⁴. At this point, the pH of the suspension is just below the point of zero charge (PZC) of HAP (6.8). It is well known that a protein molecule goes on acquiring

Fig. 2. A plot showing the effect of temperature on the adsorbed amount of gelatin

increasing negative charges when the pH is raised beyond its isoelectric point. Thus, on increasing the pH after 3.5, the gelatin molecules acquire increasing negative charges, while at the same time the HAP surfaces acquire decreasing positive charges upto 6.8 (PZC of HAP). The reason of decreased adsorption in the pH range 3.5–6.8 is that the electrostatic attraction between the gelatin molecules and HAP is opposed by the electrostatic repulsion between the negative charged O of the P–OH groups of HAP (i.e., $\text{P-O}^\delta - \text{H}^{+\delta}$) and negatively charged gelatin molecules. One more point is the adsorption of water molecules via the mechanism,

Thus, the $\text{H}^{+\delta}$ atoms of P–OH groups are no longer available for adsorbing negatively charged gelatin molecules.

Conclusions . Gelatin adsorbs onto hydroxyapatite surfaces from its aqueous solution following the Langmuir isotherm equation. The adsorption increases with increasing concentration of gelatin solution while it is significantly reduced by increasing pH of the solution. An increase in temperature also brings about an increase in the amount of adsorbed gelatin. The surface of HAP crystals is found to possess OH^- ion in their crystal lattices and P–OH groups on their surface as confirmed by ir studies

Experimental

The acid processed gelatin (MW 65000, isoelectric point 4.8)^{15,16} (Loba Chemie) was used as such. The HAP used as an adsorbent was synthesized by the reported method¹⁷. The surface area of HAP determined from BET measurements was found to be $60 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$.

Adsorption study was carried out by direct contact method which involved shaking gelatin solution (20 ml) containing HAP (0.2 g) at pH 5.7 for 2 h. After the equilibrium time, HAP was removed by centrifugation and the supernatant solution was analyzed to estimate the adsorbed amount of gelatin colorimetrically¹⁸.

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